

Antibody Characterization Report for **CSNK1A1 (Uniprot ID: P48729)**

YCharOS Antibody Characterization Report

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Target:

Short name used in this report: CSNK1A1

Recommended protein name: Casein kinase I isoform alpha

Gene name: *CSNK1A1*

Uniprot: P48729

We are a third-party organization with the mission to characterize commercial antibodies for all human protein through open science [1]. In this study, we characterized ten CSNK1A1 (corresponding gene is *CSNK1A1*) commercial antibodies for western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence using a standardized experimental protocol [2] based on genetic strategies. The *CSNK1A1* gene is essential for cell viability as evaluated using DepMap (DepMap.org). Thus, an siRNA was used to **knockdown (KD)** the *CSNK1A1* mRNA. HCT 116 was selected based on evidence of appropriate CSNK1A1 protein expression determined through DepMap [3, 4] and in Figure 2. We identified well-performing antibodies and encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibody for their specific needs.

The authors do not provide an assessment of the quality of the tested antibodies as their respective performances are limited to our finite experimental conditions. The readers should interpret the present findings based on their own scientific expertise. The authors acknowledge that an antibody that demonstrates specificity in the stated test conditions can be suboptimal in a different experimental format or in cell lines that differ from those directly tested here.

Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
Abcam	ab255451	CVCL_0291	HCT 116	WT
ATCC	HTB-14	CVCL_0022	U-87 MG	WT
ATCC	CRL-2062	CVCL_1177	DMS 53	WT
ATCC	CCL-121	CVCL_0317	HT-1080	WT
Abcam	ab255449	CVCL_0063	HEK293T	WT
ATCC	HTB-96	CVCL_0042	U-2 OS	WT
Abcam	ab255448	CVCL_0030	HeLa	WT
Horizon Discovery	C631	CVCL_Y019	HAP1	WT

Table 2: Summary of the CSNK1A1 antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µl)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab108296**	1015306-2	AB_10864123	Recombinant-mono	EPR1961(2)	rabbit	0.35	Wb
Abcam	ab206652**	1045172-2	AB_2925161	Recombinant-mono	EPR19824	rabbit	0.64	Wb, IP
Abclonal	A9308**	4000001860	AB_2863708	Recombinant-mono	ARC1860	rabbit	0.80	Wb
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP51843	QC24062-43315	AB_2045492	Polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.50	Wb
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP76053	QC48381-42018	AB_3073938	Polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.50	Wb
Bio-Techne	AF4569	ZSM0120091	AB_2084642	Polyclonal	-	sheep	0.20	Wb
Bio-Techne	NBP3-22219**	231009	AB_3075892	Recombinant-mono	SR1581	rabbit	n/a	Wb
Proteintech	55192-1-AP	00060980	AB_11183034	Polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.45	Wb, IP, IF
Proteintech	68434-1-Ig*	10037603	AB_3073926	Monoclonal	1E2E7	mouse	1.00	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-38189**	YJ4090056	AB_2898106	Recombinant-mono	ARC1860	rabbit	0.80	Wb

Wb=western blot, IP= immunoprecipitation, IF=immunofluorescence, *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody, n/a=not available

Materials and methods

Antibodies

All the CSNK1A1 antibodies tested are listed in Table 2. Peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-rabbit and anti-mouse are from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 65-6120 and 62-6520). Peroxidase-conjugated donkey anti-sheep antibody is from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A16041). Alexa-555-conjugated goat anti-rabbit and anti-mouse secondary antibodies are from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A-21429 and A-21424). Alexa-555-conjugated donkey anti-sheep secondary antibody is from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A-21436).

Cell culture

HCT 116 cells were cultured in DMEM high glucose (GE Healthcare cat. number SH30081.01) containing 10% fetal bovine serum (Wisent, cat. number 080450), 2 mM L-glutamine (Wisent cat. number 609-065, 100 IU penicillin and 100 µg/ml streptomycin (Wisent cat. number 450201). All other cell types were cultured as recommended by the provider.

Knockdown

Cell lines used are listed in Table 1. HCT 116 were treated twice with 10 nM of *CSNK1A1* SMARTpool siRNA (Horizon Discovery, cat. number L-003957-00-0005). Lipofectamine RNAiMAX (Thermo, cat. number 13778030) was used to transfect the siRNA following the manufacturer's protocol.

Antibody screening by western blot

Western blots were performed as described in our standard operating procedure [5]. HCT 116 WT and *CSNK1A1* KD (listed in Table 1) were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 89901) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at ~110,000xg for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and western blot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder from GeneDireX (cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western blots were performed with precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number WXP42012BOX) ran with Tris/Glycine/SDS buffer from Bio-Rad (cat. number 1610772), loaded in Laemmli loading sample buffer from Thermo Fisher

Scientific (cat. number AAJ61337AD) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual western blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) from Cell Signaling (cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of ~0.2 µg/ml in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 32106) or Clarity Western ECL Substrate from Bio-Rad (cat. number 1705061) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A44240).

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Immunoprecipitation was performed as described in our standard operating procedure [6]. Antibody-beads conjugates were prepared by adding 2 µg (antibody at known concentration) or 10 µl of NBP3-22219** (antibody at an unknown concentration) to 500 µl of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 87788) in a microcentrifuge tube, together with with 30µl of Dynabeads protein A- (for rabbit antibodies) or protein G- (for mouse and sheep antibodies) from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 10002D and 10004D, respectively). Tubes were rocked for ~1 hr at 4°C followed by two washes to remove unbound antibodies.

HCT 116 WT were collected in Pierce IP buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40 and 5% glycerol) supplemented with protease inhibitor. Lysates were rocked 30 min at 4°C and spun at 110,000xg for 15 min at 4°C. 0.5 ml aliquots at 2.0 mg/ml of lysate were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~1 hr at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 ml of IP lysis buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and western blot on precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels. VeriBlot for IP Detection Reagent:HRP (Abcam, cat. number ab131366) was used as a secondary detection system at a concentration of 0.1 µg/ml.

Antibody screening by immunofluorescence

Immunofluorescence was performed as described in our standard operating procedure [7]. HCT 116 WT and *CSNK1A1* KD were labelled with a green and a far-red fluorescence dye, respectively. The fluorescent dyes used are from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number C2925 and C34565). WT and KD cells were plated in a 96-well plate with optically clear flat-bottom.

(Perkin Elmer, cat. number 6055300) as a mosaic and incubated for 24 hrs in a cell culture incubator. Cells were fixed in 4% PFA (in PBS) for 15 min at room temperature and then washed 3 times with PBS. Cells were permeabilized in PBS with 0,1% Triton X-100 for 10 min at room temperature and blocked with PBS with 5% BSA, 5% goat serum and 0.01% Triton X-100 for 30 min at room temperature. Cells were incubated with IF buffer (PBS, 5% BSA, 0,01% Triton X-100) containing the primary CSNK1A1 antibodies O/N at 4°C. Cells were then washed 3 × 10 min with IF buffer and incubated with corresponding Alexa Fluor 555-conjugated secondary antibodies in IF buffer at a dilution of 1.0 µg/ml for 1 hr at room temperature with DAPI. Cells were washed 3 × 10 min with IF buffer and once with PBS.

Images were acquired on an ImageXpress micro confocal high-content microscopy system (Molecular Devices), using a 20x NA 0.95 water immersion objective and scientific CMOS cameras, equipped with 395, 475, 555 and 635 nm solid state LED lights (lumencor Aura III light engine) and bandpass filters to excite DAPI, Cellmask Green, Alexa-555 and Cellmask Red, respectively. Images had pixel sizes of 0.68 x 0.68 microns, and a z-interval of 4 microns. For analysis and visualization, shading correction (shade only) was carried out for all images. Then, maximum intensity projections were generated using 3 z-slices. Segmentation was carried out separately on maximum intensity projections of Cellmask channels using CellPose 1.0, and masks were used to generate outlines and for intensity quantification. Figures were assembled with Adobe Illustrator.

Figure 1: CSNK1A1 antibody screening by western blot

Figure 2: CSNK1A1 western blot on various cell lines

Figure 3: CSNK1A1 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Figure 4: CSNK1A1 antibody screening by immunofluorescence

Figure 1: CSNK1A1 antibody screening by western blot.

Lysates of HCT 116 WT and *CSNK1A1* KD were prepared, and 50 µg of protein were processed for western blot with the indicated CSNK1A1 antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. Antibody dilution used: ab108296** at 1/1000, ab206652** at 1/1000, A9308** at 1/1000, ARP51843 at 1/500, ARP76053 at 1/500, AF4569 at 1/100, NBP3-22219** at 1/500, 55192-1-AP 1/2000, 68434-1-Ig* at 1/3000, MA5-38189** at 1/1000. Predicted band size: 39 kDa. *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody

Figure 2: CSNK1A1 western blot on various cell lines.

Lysates of HCT 116, U-87 MG, DMS 53, HT-1080, HEK293T, U-2 OS, HeLa and HAP1 were prepared, and 20 µg of protein were processed for western blot with the indicated Casein kinase I isoform alpha antibody A9308** at 1/1000. The Ponceau stained transfer is shown as a loading control.

Figure 3: CSNK1A1 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation.

HCT 116 lysates were prepared, and immunoprecipitation was performed using 2.0 µg of the indicated CSNK1A1 antibodies pre-coupled to Dynabeads protein A or protein G. Samples were washed and processed for western blot with the indicated CSNK1A1 antibody. For western blot, ab206652** was used at 1/1000. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. SM=4% starting material; UB=4% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitate; HC=antibody heavy chain. *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody

Figure 4: CSNK1A1 antibody screening by immunofluorescence.

HCT 116 WT and *CSNK1A1* KD cells were labelled with a green or a far-red fluorescent dye, respectively. WT and KD cells were mixed and plated to a 1:1 ratio in a 96-well plate with optically clear flat-bottom. Cells were stained with the indicated CSNK1A1 antibodies and with the corresponding Alexa-fluor 555 coupled secondary antibody including DAPI. Acquisition of the blue (nucleus-DAPI), green (identification of WT cells), red (antibody staining) and far-red (identification of KD cells) channels was performed. Representative images of the blue and red (grayscale) channels are shown. WT and KD cells are outlined with green and magenta dashed line, respectively. Antibody dilution used: ab108296** at 1/350, ab206652** at 1/600, A9308** at 1/800, ARP51843 at 1/250, ARP76053 at 1/250, AF4569 at 1/100, NBP3-22219** at 1/500, 55192-1-AP 1/400, 68434-1-Ig* at 1/500, MA5-38189** at 1/800. Bars = 10 µm. *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody

References

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